

THE STRAIGHT LINE COMPLEXITY OF SMALL FACTORIALS AND PRIMORIALS

Klas Markström

*Department of Mathematics and Mathematical Statistics, Umeå University,
Umeå, Sweden*

Klas.Markstrom@math.umu.se

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Abstract

In this paper we determine the straight-line complexity of $n!$ for $n \leq 22$ and give bounds for the complexities up to $n = 46$. In the same way we determine the straight-line complexity of the product of the first primes up to $p = 23$ and give bounds for $p \leq 43$. Our results are based on an exhaustive computer search of the short length straight-line programs.

1. Introduction

In [10], Shub and Smale studied the complexity of a number of different algebraic problems in terms of the number of ring operations needed to compute a given ring element by a *straight line program*. A straight line program for an integer y can be described as a sequence of tuples $x_k = (x_i \circ x_j)$, where $i \leq j < k$, $x_1 = 1$, \circ can be any of $+$, $-$, \times , and the final element x_f is equal to y . The smallest integer f such that there exists a straight line program of length f is called the *straight line complexity*, or *cost*, of y and is denoted by $\tau(y)$.

In [2], a general complexity theory for computation over rings was introduced (see also [1]), and here the ultimate complexity of $n!$ turned out to be of great interest. For an integer x the *ultimate complexity* $\tau'(x)$ is defined as the minimum $\tau(y)$ for all y which are integer multiples of x . In particular, if there exists a constant c such that $\tau'(n!)$ is less than $(\log n)^c$ then this would lead to a fast algorithm for factoring integers; see the discussion in [4, 5]. The non-existence of such a constant c would imply that $P \neq NP$ over the complex numbers [10] and provide strong lower bounds for several important problems in complexity theory; see [3] and [8].

The results of [6, 7, 10] provide upper and lower bounds for the straight line complexity of general integers and imply that for most integers $\tau(n)$ is not $O(p(\log \log n))$ for any polynomial p . In [9], similar bounds were derived for functions over finite

fields. The known bounds for a general integer n are

$$\log_2(\log_2 n) + 1 \leq \tau(n) \leq 2 \log_2 n. \quad (1)$$

The lower bound is optimal since $\tau(2^{2^k}) = k + 1$. The upper bound is achieved by first computing the necessary powers of 2 and then adding them according to the binary expansion of n .

For specific integers, such as $n!$, there are few results that strengthen the general bounds. However for $n!$, Cheng derived an improved algorithm, conditional on a conjecture regarding the distribution of smooth integers, and earlier [11] a weaker, unconditional bound was derived by Strassen.

The purpose of this short note is to report the *exact* values of $\tau'(n!)$ for small values of n and likewise for $\tau'(p\#)$, where $p\#$ is the *primorial*, which is the product of all primes less than or equal to p . It is easy to see that, given a short straight line program for $p\#$, we can also find one for $n!$ by using repeated squaring. Our results were obtained by first doing an exhaustive computer search of all straight line programs up to a given length followed by an extended search, adapted to finding programs for $n!$ and $p\#$.

Most of the material in this note was originally part of a longer paper but while preparing that paper the author found out that the non-computational results were already covered by other recently published papers. That was over ten years ago but given the slow progress on problems in this area we hope that these exact results and bounds will help draw attention to the problems and stimulate interest among new researchers. Additions to the material from the older paper is a recomputation of all data using a newly written program and as a result of this an improvement of some of the lower bounds, and the addition of data for the straight line complexity of the factorials and primorials, instead of only their ultimate complexities.

2. Searching for Optimal Straight Line Programs

Our bounds have been found by doing an exhaustive search of the set of all straight line programs of a given length. In Appendix A we give a more detailed description of how the search was performed. In Figure 1 we display some statistics for the straight line programs. We say that an integer y has been *reached* if there is a straight line program of length at most k which computes y , and that y has been *covered* if y is a divisor of x_j for some $j \leq k$. We also include the length of the longest interval of the form $[1, \dots, x]$ in which all integers have been reached and covered respectively.

Full data from the search were saved up to $k = 9$, after which the space requirements for the full set of programs became prohibitive. For larger k we instead extended the search to higher values of k for specific target integers, in particular the

k	Size of reached set	Initial interval	Covered interval	Covered set
1	2	2	2	2
2	4	4	4	4
3	9	6	6	8
4	26	12	12	27
5	102	40	43	125
6	562	112	138	970
7	4363	310	705	13384
8	46154	1820	3546	337096
9	652227	10266	26686	19040788

Figure 1: Statistics for straight line programs of length at most 9

different factorials, primorials and multiples of them. A complete search of this type was made up to $k = 11$, thereby finding the optimal program for the cases where the length is at most 11 and providing a lower bound of 12 for the remaining target integers. For certain target integers the complete search could be extended further thanks to the efficiency in pruning the search tree for larger targets, as described in Appendix A. We also performed searches to extend some heuristically chosen straight line programs, hoping to find improved upper bounds for some cases.

In Figure 2 we show the exact values for $\tau'(n!)$ for $n \leq 28$ and for each such n an example of an optimal straight line program. For larger n we display the best method found by our partial search. The final column states whether the method is optimal or not, and otherwise the lowest possible value. In Figure 3 we show the exact values for $\tau(n!)$ for $n \leq 14$, and upper and lower bounds for some larger values of n .

Similarly Figures 4 and 5 give exact values and bounds for the small primorials, and multiples of them.

The optimal methods are noticeably better than the upper bound for $\tau(n!)$ given in inequality (1). The method of Strassen [11] gives a bound $\tau(n!) = \mathcal{O}(\sqrt{n} \log^2 n)$, which seems to deviate more and more from the optimal methods for larger n . The conditional method of Cheng [5] has a complexity of the form $\mathcal{O}(\exp(c\sqrt{\log n \log \log n}))$, which certainly seems compatible with the results for small n , but is so sensitive to the value of the constant c that very little can be said based on small values of n .

The function $\tau'(n!)$ is a monotone increasing function however it is not obvious that $\tau(n!)$ is. We end this note with an open problem.

Problem 2.1. *Is $\tau(n!)$ a monotone function?*

For small n Table 2 shows that $\tau(n!)$ is monotone, but we would not find it surprising if this fails for larger n .

n	f	Program	Lower bound
2	1	{1, 1, +}	Opt
3	3	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, *}	Opt
4	4	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {2, 3, +}, {3, 4, *}	Opt
5	5	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 1, -}, {4, 5, *}	Opt
6-7	6	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 4, -}	Opt
8-10	7	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 4, -}, {7, 7, *}	Opt
11-14	9	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {5, 3, +}, {6, 4, *}, {7, 2, -}, {7, 8, *}, {9, 9, *}	Opt
15-17	10	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 6, *}, {5, 7, -}, {8, 8, *}, {8, 9, -}, {9, 10, *}	Opt
18-19	11	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 2, +}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 4, -}, {6, 7, *}, {6, 8, *}, {9, 7, -}, {9, 10, *}, {11, 11, *}	Opt
20-22	12	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {3, 5, +}, {6, 4, *}, {2, 7, -}, {7, 8, *}, {9, 9, *}, {10, 5, -}, {10, 11, *}, {10, 12, *}	Opt
23-28	14	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 6, *}, {5, 7, *}, {8, 4, -}, {8, 9, *}, {10, 9, -}, {8, 11, +}, {10, 12, *}, {13, 13, *}, {14, 14, *},	Opt
29-34	16	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 6, *}, {5, 7, *}, {8, 4, -}, {8, 9, *}, {10, 9, -}, {8, 11, +}, {10, 12, *}, {13, 13, *}, {14, 14, *}, {7, 4, -}, {14, 15, *}	14
35-46	17	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {5, 5, *} {6, 6, *}, {5, 7, *}, {8, 4, -}, {8, 9, *} {10, 9, -}, {10, 11, +}, {11, 12, *}, {13, 6, -} {11, 14, *}, {15, 15, *}, {16, 16, *}, {17, 17, *}	14

Figure 2: Straight line programs for multiples of $n!$

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Appendix

Our bounds have been found by doing a two stage search of the set of all straight line programs of a given length.

Definition 2.2. A straight line program is *normalized* if

- (1) $x_i \neq x_j$ if $i \neq j$
- (2) $x_i > 0$ for all i .

It is easy to see that an optimal straight line program for an integer n must satisfy (1) of the above definition, and that every n has an optimal straight line program which satisfies (2).

Further we say that two straight line programs p_1 and p_2 , both of length k , are *range-isomorphic* if the sequence of numbers computed by p_2 is a permutation of the sequence computed by p_1 . It is easy to see that this is an equivalence relation on the set of straight line programs.

Our search for optimal straight line programs was performed in two stages. First we found one representative for each range-isomorphism equivalence class of the normalized straight line programs of length up to $k = 9$. Second, a search targeted at specific integers was performed.

The first stage was done as follows, starting from the initial straight line program just containing the number 1.

1. Increase k by 1 and continue.
2. Extend all programs of length $k - 1$ by one step in every possible way. Discard those of the resulting programs which are not normalized.
3. Reduce the set of all programs of length k by only keeping one representative for each range-isomorphism equivalence class.
4. Repeat from 1.

Step 3 is done since if one replaces an initial segment p_0 , of length t , of a straight line program p_1 by a range-isomorphic straight line program p'_0 then we can modify, by changing some of the indices, the resulting program to a new program p'_1 which computes the same set of numbers as p_1 . So, if p_1 was an optimal program for some integer N then p'_1 is also optimal for N .

After stage 1 is done we have found optimal programs for all integers N with $\tau(N) \leq 9$, and have shown that $\tau(N) \geq 10$ for all other integers.

After the set of programs of length 9 had been found in this way we went on with the second stage search. For each target integer N , such that $\tau(N) \geq 10$ each program of length 9 was extended in a targeted depth-first search.

Given a target integer N , each straight line program of length 9, found in the first stage search, was recursively extended by one operation, up to a specified maximum length K , with the following pruning criteria.

1. If the current program p computes the target N then save the program and do not extend it further.
2. If the current program p is not normalized then do not extend it further.
3. If the current program has length k and the maximum integer x which it has computed satisfies $x^{2^{(K-k)}} < N$ then do not extend it further.

The third condition is included since if a program p of this type is extended by $K - k$ steps then the resulting program cannot compute an integer as large as the target N , if $k \geq 2$.

Using this depth-first search strategy each program of length 9 was extended to $k = 11$ for each of our target integers. For the larger target integers the search could be completed for larger values of k as well, thanks to the more restrictive bound in the third pruning criterion, thus providing larger lower bounds for the optimal straight line programs, and proving the optimality of the some of the programs found.

n	f	Program	Lower bound
2	1	{1, 1, +}	Opt
3	3	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, *}	Opt
4	4	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {2, 3, +}, {3, 4, *}	Opt
5	6	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {1, 3, +}, {3, 4, *}, {5, 2, -}, {5, 6, *}	Opt
6	6	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {3, 3, *}, {3, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 4, -}	Opt
7	7	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, *}, {2, 4, *}, {4, 5, *}, {6, 2, -}, {6, 7, *}	Opt
8	8	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {1, 3, +}, {3, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 4, -}, {6, 7, *}, {8, 2, -}	Opt
9	8	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, *}, {2, 4, *}, {4, 5, *}, {6, 2, -}, {6, 7, *}, {7, 8, *}	Opt
10	9	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, +}, {2, 4, +}, {4, 5, +}, {6, 6, *}, {4, 7, *}, {5, 8, *}, {8, 9, *}	Opt
11	9	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {3, 3, *}, {3, 4, +}, {4, 5, *}, {3, 6, +}, {5, 7, *}, {8, 6, -}, {8, 9, *}	Opt
12	10	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {3, 3, *}, {2, 4, +}, {4, 5, *}, {4, 6, +}, {7, 7, *}, {8, 4, -}, {6, 9, *}, {5, 10, *}	Opt
13	11	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {1, 3, +}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 5, *}, {3, 6, +}, {5, 6, *}, {7, 8, *}, {7, 9, *}, {10, 4, -}, {9, 11, *}	Opt
14	11	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {3, 3, *}, {3, 4, +}, {2, 5, +}, {5, 6, +}, {5, 7, *}, {6, 8, *}, {4, 9, *}, {10, 8, -}, {10, 11, *}	Opt
15	12	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {2, 3, *}, {1, 4, +}, {3, 5, *}, {6, 4, -}, {6, 7, *}, {8, 4, -}, {6, 9, *}, {10, 6, +}, {8, 11, *}, {10, 12, *}	Opt
16	12	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {2, 3, +}, {3, 4, +}, {3, 4, *}, {4, 5, *}, {6, 7, +}, {6, 7, *}, {9, 5, -}, {8, 9, *}, {10, 11, *}, {11, 12, *}	Opt
17	12	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {2, 3, +}, {2, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 3, -}, {5, 6, +}, {6, 7, *}, {8, 9, *}, {4, 10, *}, {11, 9, -}, {11, 12, *}	Opt
18	13	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, *}, {3, 4, *}, {3, 5, +}, {6, 6, *}, {5, 7, +}, {6, 8, +}, {5, 9, *}, {7, 10, *}, {7, 11, *}, {12, 10, -}, {11, 13, *}	Opt
19	13	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 2, -}, {4, 2, +}, {4, 5, *}, {7, 3, -}, {6, 6, *}, {7, 9, *}, {9, 10, *}, {11, 7, -}, {11, 12, *}, {8, 13, *}	Opt
20	14	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {3, 3, *}, {1, 4, +}, {3, 5, *}, {6, 4, -}, {7, 7, *}, {8, 3, -}, {8, 4, -}, {5, 9, +}, {5, 11, *}, {9, 10, *}, {13, 13, *}, {12, 14, *}	13

Figure 3: Straight line programs for $n!$

p	f	Program	lower bound
2	1	{1, 1, +}	Opt
3	3	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, *}	Opt
5	5	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {4, 5, -}	Opt
7	6	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {4, 6, -}	Opt
11	7	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {3, 3, *}, {3, 4, *}, {3, 5, +}, {6, 6, *}, {3, 7, -}	Opt
13	8	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 6, *}, {7, 7, *}, {4, 8, -}	Opt
17	9	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 6, *}, {7, 7, *}, {8, 8, *}, {9, 5, -}	Opt
19- 23	10	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {5, 2, -}, {6, 6, *}, {7, 7, *}, {8, 8, *}, {9, 9, *}, {10, 8, -}	Opt
29- 31	11	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, +}, {2, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 6, *}, {7, 4, +}, {7, 5, +}, {9, 3, +}, {9, 8, *}, {11, 10, *}	Opt
37- 43	14	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {3, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 6, *}, {5, 7, *}, {8, 4, -}, {8, 9, *}, {10, 9, -}, {10, 11, +}, {11, 12, *}, {13, 6, -}, {11, 14, *}	13

Figure 4: Straight line programs for multiples of $p\#$

p	f	Program	lower bound
2	1	{1, 1, +}	Opt
3	3	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, *}	Opt
5	5	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, +}, {2, 3, *}, {4, 5, *}	Opt
7	6	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, +}, {3, 4, *}, {5, 1, -}, {5, 6, *}	Opt
11	7	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, *}, {2, 4, +}, {4, 5, *}, {6, 6, *}, {4, 7, +}	Opt
13	8	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, +}, {2, 4, *}, {5, 5, *}, {6, 6, *}, {5, 7, +}, {3, 8, *}	Opt
17	9	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, *}, {3, 3, *}, {1, 4, +}, {3, 5, +}, {2, 5, *}, {6, 7, *}, {1, 8, +}, {8, 9, *}	Opt
19	10	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, *}, {4, 4, *}, {4, 5, *}, {6, 4, -}, {6, 1, -}, {8, 8, *}, {9, 5, -}, {10, 7, *}	Opt
23	11	{1, 1, +}, {1, 2, +}, {2, 3, +}, {2, 4, *}, {5, 3, +}, {5, 6, *}, {5, 7, *}, {5, 8, +}, {9, 9, *}, {10, 1, -1}, {11, 7, *}	Opt
29	13	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {3, 3, *}, {2, 4, +}, {1, 5, +}, {2, 6, *}, {7, 7, *}, {6, 8, +}, {4, 9, +}, {4, 10, +}, {2, 9, *}, {10, 11, *}, {12, 13, *}	12
31	15	{1, 1, +}, {2, 2, +}, {3, 3, *}, {2, 4, +}, {1, 5, +}, {2, 6, *}, {7, 7, *}, {6, 8, +}, {4, 9, +}, {4, 10, +}, {2, 9, *}, {10, 11, *}, {12, 13, *}, {4, 1, -}, {14, 15, *}	12

Figure 5: Straight line programs for $p\#$